

Open Information-Educational Environment Options

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Annotatsiya:

Education and open learning environment of the school in the education process in this article from the use of information problems, get information on open research and analysis of the learning environment of the scientists borli options didactic lit.

Base words: open information environment, education, individual, multimedia, teaching tools, and intellectual abilities.

For school free information-educational environmentand the methodology they use a wide range of opportunities to develop the use of topical and its remains [1, 2].

Today, the opportunities in the organization of the educational process effective information and education environment of the expansion of the educational process serves as an effective tool to. One of these resources open information-educational environment , it has a special feature for secondary educational institutions. Open information-educational environment,the advantages of mamlakatimz options and the commonwealth of independent states, in particular Mirsanov u. m., J.A.ELMURODOV N.V.Yarchikova, V.K.We Have Vinni, E.L.Gavrilov, A.X.Gilmutdinov, A.N.Jivenkov A.Yu.Zaxarov, like many scientific basis given by scientists.

However, the research work of these scientists in the school of science teaching in open information-educational environmenthas not been enough research in options. Therefore, the process of education and school of education to open an information-educational environmentof pedagogical practice is born of the necessity of a wider survey of opportunities in's. In order to do this pedagogical should get clarification of its responsibilities.

Meanwhile, the introduction of computer technologies in the educational process of the school, his the task of teaching, there are three different directions [3]:

- teach students: to increase the effectiveness of science teaching;
- the formation of a certain style;
- thinking of readers, and knowledge of interest to activate.

The successful solution of these tasks free information-educational environment serves an important pedagogical tool.

In this regard, I.G.Zaxarovaning, according to the information and education environment in the organization of education and the possibilities of effective training process is high, almost touch interactive educational environment on the basis of a lot of them live to create active, that is, independently serves as an important system in the development of knowledge and intellectual ability [4]. All of these thoughts directly to increase the knowledge and interest of the readers, if woke aimed at, directed to the computer at various levels of education refers to the use of methodical system.

Open information-educational environment and designed by students mastering the content of education to the development of a pedagogical tool. In this regard S.L.Atanasyanning according to the information-educational environment to provide independent information related to science in the online form and increases the opportunity to get an education [5].

Electronic learning environment in the emergence of new types of approaches that have been applied to the picture, the rejection does not mean full of traditional textbooks. The design of the traditional textbook has accumulated a great experience in the field of imaging, then the charm of their pictures, psychological and spatial context of the elements and features selected publications psixofiziologik guruhlash, elements of the particular physiological aspects of color perception (release pressing the accuracy, font and other properties), with attention difference [1].

Open information-educational environmentin the training data in two-dimensional and three-dimensional graphic images (photos, diagrams, graphs, schemes),; voice, video, and animated in the form of rollers is provided. This tool is provided with the help of educational subjects related to many of the open information-educational environment is created. They are interactive, using a wide range of the educational process as a teaching tool it is.

In the meantime, open learning environment, information and interactive and adapted to the specific qualities different types of data, as well as to take into account the individual characteristics of the readers, their motivation which will help you improve your effective online education technology.

Open information-educational environment and provide many types of information using computer technology and the study of the meaningful combination-allows you to provide data in different forms: painting, including scan photos, maps and presentations; voice recordings; video effects; and animated simulyatorlar animasion.

As a rule, from the visual aspect along with attractive pictures or be more attractive than static text animated presentations provided the desired emotions filling maintain the level of the training data, will help to increase the effectiveness of the training.

Open information-educational environmentof human uniqueness and the essence of mental perception, thinking, including the formation and development of affects. The main source of information, which is near the time until the printed text, the content is based on the principle mavhumlashtirish from the realities of simplicity and in most cases it is organized as a sequence of phrases in order to read oddiydan looking at this while thinking skills activities shape, similar to the composition of the printed text has a structure has the following characteristics: linear consistency, analytical ierarxik and others [1].

Open information-educational environment from the use of the process in the various sciences students, events, and allow you to demonstrate geometric forms. That is, in the context of different training methods can be used: read, listen and see through educational video products. Education secondary education in the process of school education and this information is open-education environment gives students the chance to get through in order to use the different education – education-how in order information, including the development of interactive media with their peers and use the opportunities of the united assignments carried out in any order to decide. As a result, students will become an active participant of the educational process.

Scientific-research the analysis of the results shows that in the school of science of the internet in the educational process designed to open the information-educational environment following the introduction provides wide range of opportunities:

- the organization of independent work of students;
- search and problematic stimulation of practical activity (interactive relations with a variety of educational resources, the use of text giperhavolalardan, modeling, and others);
- the conduct of individual sessions (choose the level of difficulty of taking the individual features to manage the pace of reading and others);
- interactive teaching (ability to communicate with computer technology);
- the possibility of studying the variability of the training data;
- to update information, taking into account the change to work mode;
- educational activity quick, effective and quarterly ultimate control and self-control of the implementation;
- vizualizasiyasi and multimedia learning opportunities through the use of live-mastering the quality of data base improvements;
- access to the use of modern information technologies.

Thus, the open information-educational environment from the use of the system-activity approach to the implementation of focused individuals on the basis of developing the main pedagogical theory allows for the effective implementation of the problematic of teaching. This active through information and communication technologies creates the opportunity for independent educational and research activities in the search to create the conditions pedagogic, pedagogical knowledge and intertwined with traditional to modern didaktika innovasiyalar ensures that creates conditions for the formation and development of sustainable interest.

In this regard, V.A. According to boriseykonig for the school, open information-educational environment has a positive impact on the use of a few aspects at a time from [6]:

- expand education to build the capacity of the trajectory;
- most new educational use of resources;
- student expansion of education opportunities;
- increase the transparency of the education process;
- simplify communication with all participants of educational process;
- increase the convenience of the monitoring of the educational process;
- online submission of assignments to stimulate the formation of new conditions and educational;
- creation of conditions for the development of individual educational trajectory of the student;

- automation at the expense of bureaucratic reduce the load.

In the meantime, has the following advantages:

- perception of students in the educational process and use multiple functions at the same time, as a result, the integration of data is achieved by delivering different sensations;
- due to the dynamic of the show vizualizasiya to process abstract information;
- teach students readers: training-wide data educational, social, and historical context to create it.

Modern school for open information-educational environment of development, this type of innovation that allow you to present information using different technology and work again to a completely new level allows you to introduce the most advanced technical education.

For the teaching of science in school of open information-educational environment from the use of the user perception and understanding of information by the mechanism of changes. Change the quality to receive information when working with electronic learning resources in education gives away. Thus, the reader can see, hear, through the knowledge, skills and qualifications will have. To see the absolutely new level didactic to read through the implementation of the principles [1].

Science in school is taught from free information-educational environment for the development of spatial imagination from the use of promising. Thus, the user's cognitive, mnemonic and new forms of creative activity that will appear, this ensures the development of cognitive processes in man.

Open information-educational environment in the educational process with students in psychology should take into account more shaxslararo applied to the relationship. On the person of the teacher a positive or negative relationship occurs in the initial minutes of communicating with students. A teacher in a short time received by the students is positive, let's be incurred on how complex it through all the data are accepted. You originally received it if it is negative, then the students they choose for themselves unnecessary internal data and the evidence of disagreement begins to appear.

Therefore, the lesson in the teacher open information-educational environment in the organization should pay attention to use the following: has determined that it is important and secondary, to give you the advantage on certain tasks set; the main purpose is to define and to be the stage of its implementation; students to pay attention to the organization of meaningful activities; strive to increase the mental activity of the hearers; give instructions that can be on the errors; control the fulfillment of assignments.

Conclusion in the words of the school in the educational process information, open-learning environment necessary for today's introduction of the process of education pedagogical tool. Therefore, the use of educational goals, objectives, content and organization forms should be considered strictly.

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